

NOTES

Copper(II) Chelates of α -Thionaphthoic Hydrazide and Nicotinic Acid as Biologically Important Compounds†

SURESH K. AGARWAL* and DINESH KUMAR

Department of Chemistry, L. K. P. G. College,
Sahibabad-201 005

*Manuscript received 3 October 1989, revised 18 May 1990,
accepted 11 October 1990*

CHELATES of metal ions with acylthiohydrazides have been reported in the literature¹ but the mixed ligand chelates of copper(II) with α -thionaphthoic hydrazide as primary and nicotinic acid as co-ligand have not yet been studied.

Experimental

α -Thionaphthoic hydrazide was synthesised by using literature procedure². Chemicals and organic solvents used were of analytical grade. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were estimated by micro-analytical technique. The ir spectra were scanned on Beckmann and Perkin-Elmer 221 spectrophotometers. Sulphur was estimated as BaSO₄ and chlorine by Volhard's method. Conductance was measured in DMF at the concentration 10⁻³ M using a Systronics conductivity meter.

Preparation of the chelates: The chelates were prepared in two steps. In the first step, copper(II) salts were dissolved in ethanol and the thiohydrazide solution (10 mmol) was gradually added. The reaction mixture was thoroughly stirred and refluxed over a water-bath at about 70° for 0.5 h. The greenish compounds separated were filtered, washed with a little of alcohol, acetonitrile and dry ether and dried. In the second step, nicotinic acid solution (10 mmol) was added to the aqueous suspension

of the complexes with continuous shaking. The mixed solution was refluxed for 3–4 h at 80°. The metal chelates separated as crystalline products on cooling at room temperature, were filtered, washed with ethanol and dry ether and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl₂.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses (Table 1) show 1:1:1 (M–L–L') stoichiometry in the isolated chelates (where L= α -th H and L'=nic H). The low conductance values (4.2–6.1 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹) in DMF at a concentration 10⁻³ M indicate their non-electrolytic behaviour. The mixed chelates are insoluble in water and common organic solvents but they dissolve appreciably in DMF and DMSO. The compounds are stable and non-hygroscopic.

The reflectance spectra of the chelates exhibit a broad band at 14 400–14 950 cm⁻¹, corresponding to ²E_g→²T_{2g} transition³ in octahedral field.

In the ir spectra of mixed chelates, thioamide bands I and II show a positive shift of about 40 cm⁻¹ while band IV gets shifted to a low frequency (~810 cm⁻¹). The changes in the band positions suggest that thiohydrazide coordinates through thione sulphur. Further, the bands observed at 3 150–3 250 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of α -thionaphthoic hydrazide, characteristic of δ_{NH_2} and ν_{NH_2} , are converted into single broad band existing at 3 280–3 150 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. This shows the participation of the terminal nitrogen atom in the complexation process which is further evidenced by a slight negative shift (~10 cm⁻¹) of NH₂ deformation band⁴ observed at 1 595 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of thiohydrazide. The C–C, C=N and heterocyclic ring stretching absorptions existing in the spectrum of nicotinic acid are shifted to higher frequency bands

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND THERMAL DATA OF COPPER(II) CHELATES

Compd.*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				% Loss at 150–180° Found/(Calcd.)
	Metal	N	S	Cl	
[Cu(α -th H) (nic)Cl (H ₂ O)]	14.30 (14.41)	9.46 (9.52)	7.20 (7.25)	8.08 (8.03)	4.10 (4.08)
[Cu(α -th H) (nic) (NO ₂)(H ₂ O)]	13.66 (13.59)	12.05 (11.97)	6.81 (6.84)	—	3.87 (3.84)
[Cu(α -th H) (nic) (SCN)(H ₂ O)]	13.63 (13.71)	12.18 (12.08)	13.72 (13.80)	—	3.90 (3.88)
[Cu(α -th H) (nic)(Ac)(H ₂ O)]	13.60 (13.68)	9.09 (9.04)	6.93 (6.88)	—	3.90 (3.87)

* α -th H= α -Thionaphthoic hydrazide, nic=nicotinic acid (deprotonated), Ac=acetate.

†Presented in National Seminar on 'Role of Young Scientists in National Development' at Multani Mal Modi College, Modinagar, 1989.

*For correspondence: III-E 7/9, Nehru Nagar, Ghaziabad-201 001.

(1 640vs, 1 605 and 1 485 cm^{-1}) in the complexes which is suggestive of the donation of electrons from ring nitrogen to the metal. The appearance of bands at 1 590 and 1 400 cm^{-1} corresponding to ν_{COO} shows the chelation through the oxygen atom of the deprotonated carboxyl group.

Some non-ligand bands also exist in the lower frequency region (480–350 cm^{-1}) which may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$, $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$. The band observed at $\sim 210 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the halo complex may be due to $\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$. In the nitrate and acetato complexes, the bands found in the spectra show their monodentate behaviour. In the thiocyanato complex, the $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ and δ_{NCS} bands found at 825 cm^{-1} and 475 cm^{-1} show N-bonded to metal atom. The appearance of a strong broad band at $\sim 3\,460 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a medium intensity band at 830 cm^{-1} in the chelates are indicative of the presence of coordinated water which is further confirmed by the percentage loss data (Table 1) recorded in the temperature range 150–180°.

Acknowledgement

Financial assistance from C.S.I.R., New Delhi, is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. J. GABEL, E. LARSEN and P. TRINDERUP, *Acta Chem. Scand., Ser. A*, 1977, **31**, 657; K. A. JENSEN and J. F. MIQUEL, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1952, **6**, 189; J. R. DILWORTH, J. H. P. VELLA, K. VENKATA-SUBRAMANIAN and J. A. ZUBEETA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, **18**, 268; U. KUMARI, C. P. SINGH and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 255.
2. K. A. JENSEN and C. PEDERSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1961, **15**, 1097.
3. C. J. BALHAUSEN, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1955, **49**, 9383; T. S. PIPER and R. L. BELFORD, *Mol. Phys.*, 1962, **5**, 169.
4. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1977.

Complexes of Copper(II), Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) with *N*-Benzoyl-*N'*-6-amino-(pyrid-2-yl)thiocarbamide

R. K. PATEL and R. N. PATEL*

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Kourkela-769 008

Manuscript received 1 August 1989, revised 31 May 1990, accepted 12 October 1990

THE increasing commercial value of transition metal complexes with sulphur donor ligands has aroused considerable interest in the field of chemistry while their analytical application are well-known. As a part of our studies, an attempt has been made to prepare some complexes using Cu^{II} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II}

with *N*-benzoyl-*N'*-6-amino(pyrid-2-yl)thiocarbamide.

Experimental

Preparation of ligand: Equimolar amount of 2,6-diamino pyridine in acetone was added to benzoyl isothiocyanate dropwise with constant stirring¹. The mixture was refluxed for about 8 h and kept in ice-cold condition and then poured in ice-cold distilled water. The resulting syrupy liquid was kept overnight. The compound formed as a fine crystal of buff colour, was filtered, washed with acetone and recrystallised from ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Preparation of complexes: A solution of the ligand (0.2 mol) in acetone was added dropwise to a hot ethanolic solution of the metallic salt (0.1 mol) MX_2 , where $\text{M} = \text{Cu}$, Co and Ni and $\text{X} = \text{Cl}$, Br , NO_3 , ClO_4 . The solution was refluxed for 3–4 h and then 50% solvent was allowed to evaporate. The complexes formed were filtered, washed with alcohol and dried under reduced pressure. The complexes were found to be highly insoluble in water and common organic solvents. The analytical and physical data of the complexes are summarised in Table 1. Attempts to prepare perchlorate complexes of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} failed.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses of the complexes correspond to the formula ML_2X_2 . Molar conductance of the complexes in DMF solution were found to be less than 15 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ suggesting non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The molecular weight measurement by Rast's camphor method suggests the monomeric structure. The Cu^{II} complexes possess magnetic moment value of 2.0–2.2 B.M. which can be attributed to spin-orbit coupling². The Co^{II} complexes possess magnetic moment value of 3.66–3.71 B.M. which may be due to spin state equilibrium between high-spin and low-spin octahedral species³. The Ni^{II} complexes possess the magnetic moment values of 3.1–3.9 B.M. which are in accordance with octahedral complexes⁴.

The characteristic ir bands of the ligand at $\sim 3\,400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a sharp band at $3\,170 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to ν_{NH} and ν_{NH_2} respectively; the sharpness of the bands suggests that both the groups in the ligand have the same vibrational energy. The thioamide band-I ($1\,450 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), thioamide band-II ($1\,300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), thioamide band-III ($1\,070 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and thioamide band-IV (840 cm^{-1}) are observed in the ligand⁵. The band at $1\,670 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ stretching vibration⁶ of the ligand. The band at $1\,620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be due to deformation vibration of NH_2 group. Another band at $\sim 1\,570 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned⁷ to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$. Three bands at 1 250, 1 200 and 1 100 cm^{-1} may be attributed to $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ band and substituted aromatic ring respectively, which establish the structure of the ligand.